

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

Deliverable 10.5 - GEONODE geospatial platform

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

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0.1	Tim Collart (SBE)	Initial draft	07/04/2023
0.2	Stéphane Pesant (EMBL-EBI)	Review	25/07/2023
0.3	Tim Collart (SBE)	Amendments and addition of metrics section	02/05/2023
1.0	Eloïse Trabut (SZN)	Submission	17/05/2023
1.1	Meike Vogt	Addition of AtlantECO GRID in the content workflow	24/05/2023
1.2	Tim Collart (SBE)	Revision addition of section on legacy addition of practical guide in annex I	20/08/2024
2.0	Claudio de Majo (Trust-IT), Stephane Pesant (EMBL), Daniele luicone (SZN)	Final review, formatting and resubmission	02/09/2024

2 Executive summary

The AtlantECO GeoNode, available at atlanteco-geonode.eu, is an advanced geospatial web platform that will allow project partners and stakeholders to search for, visualise, download and share the AtlantECO MAPS produced by the project. In addition, it will offer a catalogue to search and download the AtlantECO BASE datasets used to create these maps.

This deliverable describes in detail the architecture of the AtlantECO GeoNode as well as the functionalities that it provides and the metrics that can be derived from it. Furthermore, it documents the workflows that will be adopted to populate the GeoNode platform with the AtlantECO MAPS and BASE data products. It also highlights how the AtlantECO GeoNode enables the dissemination of the project's research outputs through the platform itself, to the European Atlas of the Seas and to the European Marine Observation and Data network (EMODnet). Finally, it details the plan for the platform after the end of the project.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

The AtlantECO web-based GIS (further referred to as the "AtlantECO GeoNode") is based on the open-source GeoNode project¹, a geospatial content management system (CMS) and a spatial data infrastructure (SDI) platform designed to enable sharing and collaboration of geospatial data and maps. The project aims to promote the use of geospatial data and make it more accessible to people all over the world. It does this by building on state-of-the-art, open-source geospatial web technologies and standards, supported by the Open Source Geospatial Foundation (OSGeo)² and the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)³. As such, it can be customized to meet the needs of the AtlantECO project.

The AtlantECO GeoNode was launched on April 2022 and is available at <https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/>. The web platform was customized to match the look and feel of the AtlantECO project website⁴. After some tests with the AtlantECO maps NetCDF files, data population of the AtlantECO GeoNode has kicked off in the spring of 2023 and will continue throughout the lifetime of the project, as new versions and datasets become available.

The AtlantECO GeoNode aims to promote the research outputs of the project by:

- Providing a web platform that allows to search for, visualise, download and share the AtlantECO MAPS both within the project as well as to other stakeholders.
- Providing standard OGC web services that allow to search for, visualise and download AtlantECO MAPS within common Geospatial Information System (GIS) tools (e.g. QGIS, ArcGIS) as well as scripting languages (e.g. R, Python)
- Enabling wider dissemination of AtlantECO MAPS by inclusion in other web map projects like the European Atlas of the Seas⁵ that support the OGC standards.

¹ <https://geonode.org>

² <https://www.osgeo.org>

³ <https://www.ogc.org>

⁴ <https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/>

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/atlas/maritime_atlas

4 Architecture and functionalities

The AtlantECO GeoNode consists of several components (see section 4.1) which are deployed as Docker⁶ containers within a cloud-hosting environment (see section 4.2).

4.1 Components

Figure 1 presents a schematic overview of the different GeoNode components that are discussed in more detail in the sections below.

Figure 1: GeoNode architecture. Image courtesy of Corti et al. (2019), licensed under CC BY 4.0 Open Access

4.1.1 Spatial Data Store & Database

The AtlantECO GeoNode is using different types of data storage based on the type of data:

- Raster datasets (AtlantECO MAPS) will be stored on the File system of the server
- Metadata describing the datasets, as well GeoNode Users, Groups, Permissions etc. will be stored in a PostgreSQL relational database⁷. In case spatial vector-type datasets needs to be hosted, they will also be hosted in the database with the POSTGIS extension⁸.
- Other large documents (e.g. AtlantECO BASE tables) will be stored In an S3 Bucket, and linked to from the document metadata.

⁶ <https://www.docker.com>

⁷ <https://www.postgresql.org>

⁸ <https://postgis.net>

4.1.2 Spatial Data Server and Cache

The AtlantECO Maps NetCDF files stored on the file system, will be accessible through the GeoServer⁹ spatial data server, configured with the NetCDF extension¹⁰. GeoServer is an open-source Java-based application that follows the Open Geospatial Consortium's (OGC) industry-standard procedures for transferring geospatial information online, known as OGC web services. For the AtlantECO Maps datasets, these include:

- Web Mapping Service (WMS) that can be queried for geo-referenced Images (in different image formats) derived from the AtlantECO Maps data over a specific geographic range, time and depth, and applying a specific style.
- Web Coverage Service (WCS) that can be queried for a subset of the AtlantECO Maps data in a specific geographic range, time and depth in a number of raster type geospatial data formats (including GeoTIFF, ArcGRID, etc.)

The interactive map viewer in the AtlantECO GeoNode web application as well as external GIS applications can use these web services to visualise and download the AtlantECO MAPS data. In order to Improve the performance of the interactive map viewer, GeoNode employs a GeoWebCache¹¹ tiling server that stores and serves recently requested images using the WMS tile Caching (WMS-C) protocol.

Finally, the GeoFence¹² module handles data visualisation and access restrictions to specific users or user groups and can be easily configured through the GeoNode web application. Annex I provides a practical guide on how users of the AtlantECO GeoNode can interact with the OGC services using the open-source desktop GIS software QGIS.

4.1.3 Metadata Catalogue

The catalogue service provides a means for users to search metadata records and locate the associated geospatial datasets that are available. The catalogue service offered by GeoNode is built upon the widely accepted OGC Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW) standard and implemented via the open-source pycsw¹³ Python library. By using CSW requests, the catalogue service enables users to retrieve metadata records stored in the PostgreSQL tables of the GeoNode web application. This functionality can be utilized by other external catalogue applications such as GeoNetwork, QGIS MetaSearch Plugin, ArcGIS CSW Client, among others.

4.1.4 Front-end Web application

The GeoNode web application acts as a central hub that connects clients to other components of the system. It operates similar to a social media platform and offers a broad range of services, such as uploading, searching, viewing, editing, styling and downloading (meta) data. Users can create and share interactive maps by combining different data layers and setting permissions for data access. Additionally, social features like ratings, comments, and announcements enable collaboration and discussion about the data. The web application is built with Django¹⁴, an open-source Python web framework, a uWSGI Python engine¹⁵, and an nginx¹⁶ web server.

⁹ <https://geoserver.org>

¹⁰ <https://docs.geoserver.org/stable/en/user/extensions/netcdf/netcdf.html>

¹¹ <https://www.geowebcache.org>

¹² <https://docs.geoserver.org/stable/en/user/extensions/geofence-server/index.html>

¹³ <https://pycsw.org>

¹⁴ <https://djangoproject.com>

¹⁵ <https://uwsgi-docs.readthedocs.io>

¹⁶ <https://nginx.org>

The web application revolves around three primary resources that can have various properties attached, including metadata (title, abstract, author, license, etc.), rating, comments, and permissions:

- **Layers** represents spatial datasets that allow both interactive visualisation and data access through OGC web services. They can be associated with metadata and styles and linked to other resources. Layers can be created by uploading data to the local GeoNode or by connecting to external data repositories that provide OGC or ESRI web services ("remote layers"). The AtlantECO MAPS data will be provided as local layers uploaded to the AtlantECO GeoNode.
- **Maps** are combinations of different layers, and they can be drawn on top of a relevant base map, enriched with their own style and metadata, and exported as an image or embedded as an interactive map in a webpage.
- **Documents** are any other resource types, such as images, presentations, tables and reports, and can be shared with relevant partners and linked to specific data layers or maps and metadata. AtlantECO BASE data tables will be available as documents from the AtlantECO GeoNode.

4.1.4.1 User Interface

The front-end of GeoNode is designed to be modern and flexible, utilizing Django templates alongside various JavaScript libraries and frameworks. AngularJS¹⁷ is implemented to allow user access to the GeoNode Application Programming Interface (API) while jQuery¹⁸ is used for event handling, such as autocomplete functionality in search boxes. Webpage styling utilizes Bootstrap¹⁹ Cascading Style Sheets (CSS). Additionally, a map viewer is provided through MapStore²⁰, which is based on the OpenLayers²¹ mapping library and the ReactJS²² User Interface library. The GeoNode layers and maps are visualized in the map viewer, with data layers being retrieved from the GeoServer using the WMS protocol. Figure 2 shows an example of an AtlantECO MAPS dataset visualised In the AtlantECO GeoNode map viewer. A practical guide on how users can interact with the AtlantECO GeoNode users' interface to search for, visualise and download data layers is provided in Annex I.

¹⁷ <https://angularjs.org>

¹⁸ <https://jquery.com>

¹⁹ <https://getbootstrap.com>

²⁰ <https://mapstore.geosolutionsgroup.com>

²¹ <https://openlayers.org>

²² <https://react.dev>

Figure 2: Example of the interactive map viewer in the AtlantECO GeoNode, displaying one of the AtlantECO MAPS datasets.

4.1.4.2 Search Engine

The AtlantECO GeoNode utilizes Django Haystack to enable a search engine that can perform fast and scalable queries of the available metadata. The search engine's functionality is supported by Elasticsearch²³, which provides advanced search features such as fuzzy search for handling spelling errors and synonyms, search prediction and auto-completion, geographic and temporal search and more (see Figure 3).

4.1.4.3 Asynchronous Task Handling

To ensure a seamless user experience, the AtlantECO GeoNode is integrated with a task queue that uses Celery²⁴ and RabbitMQ²⁵. This task queue enables demanding operations (e.g. data uploads) to be executed asynchronously, separate from the client-server communication.

4.1.4.4 User and permission management

In the AtlantECO GeoNode, partners can create a GeoNode user accounts at <https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/account/signup>. These user accounts can then be grouped (e.g. for the full consortium, according to institution, work packages, or case study area). This allows relevant permissions for viewing, editing, and downloading metadata to be easily assigned to appropriate partners, external stakeholders, or the general public (without an account). The security and authorization features of GeoNode are implemented using the Django Guardian library. These permissions are automatically transferred to the GeoFence module of GeoServer, which also applies to the web service data access.

²³ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch>

²⁴ <https://docs.celeryq.dev>

²⁵ <https://www.rabbitmq.com>

Filters Clear

▼ TEXT

Search

> KEYWORDS

▼ TYPE

Raster Layer 1

> CATEGORIES

> RESPONSIBLE

> GROUPS

> GROUP CATEGORIES

▼ DATE

Date begins after:

Date ends before:

▼ REGIONS

Search by region

▼ EXTENT

Figure 3: AtlantECO GeoNode filters that can be applied to search for the available data layers

4.2 Cloud Infrastructure

The AtlantECO GeoNode is deployed on different Amazon Web Services (AWS), whose cost are billed monthly and depend on the compute required, the size of data stored and the traffic In and out of the system. Following AWS services are used:

- An Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2) t3a.xlarge instance (4 vCPU's & 16 GB RAM) running the Ubuntu Sever 20.04LTS AMI in the eu-west-1 (Ireland) region is used to host all GeoNode component (see Section 4.1) in separate docket containers.
- Elastic Block Store (EBS) is used to provide the file system that store the AtlantECO MAPS NetCDF files, PostgreSQL database (containing metadata) and other system configuration files. The EBS storage size can be scaled to the project needs as long as this is within the SBE budget.
- AWS Backup is used to create a weekly backup of the entire system, allowing quick recovery with minimal data loss in case of system failure.
- Simple Storage Service (S3) object storage will be used to store the AtlantECO BASE data tables and will be linked from the GeoNode metadata. The S3 storage size can be scaled to the project needs as long as this is within the SBE budget.
- Simple Email Service is used to manage emails sent by the AtlantECO GeoNode (e.g. password reset, account invitation and confirmation, etc.)
- Route 53 is used to register and configure the atlanteco-geonode.eu domain name.

5 Metrics

The AtlantECO GeoNode, as well as the AWS cloud Infrastructures it runs on, continuously collects metrics for analytics and monitoring. Below, we describe which metrics can be considered by the project for uptake as Key Performance Indicators (KPI's).

5.1 Contents and Web traffic metrics

The AtlantECO GeoNode collects a range of metrics on its contents as well as the web traffic reaching the contents. These metrics can be displayed in a dashboard (see Figure 4) on the GeoNode (only accessible to admin users) or extracted for reporting and analytics purposes.

Content metrics Include:

- Number of layers: These will be a subset of the variables in the AtlantECO MAPS files that are published In the AtlantECO GeoNode.
- Number of documents: These will be the AtlantECO BASE files published In the AtlantECO GeoNode
- Number of Maps: These are combinations of the layers that can be created by AtlantECO GeoNode users for sharing (e.g. as an embedded map in their website)
- Number of Users: These are the number of active AtlantECO GeoNode user accounts

The GeoNode collects server-side web traffic metrics:

- The number of hits: The number of requests sent to load pages of the AtlantECO GeoNode User Interface (this does not include requests sent to the OGC web services)
- Number of Anonymous Sessions: This represents the number of anonymous visitors to the AtlantECO GeoNode (Identified based on their IP address)
- Number of unique visitors: The number of authenticated AtlantECO GeoNode users that have connected. Note that this only tracks users who are authenticated so this does not accurately represent the true number of users.

These web traffic metrics can be broken down by following variables:

- The contents (Layers, Documents, Maps) visited
- The country of origin (based on the IP address of the request)
- The device type from where the requests were made (based on HTTP header)
- The Browser type from where the requests were made (based on HTTP header)

Figure 4: Web Traffic Analytics dashboard of the AtlantECO GeoNode (only available to admin users) on 02/05/2023

5.2 Resource Monitoring Metrics

Continues monitoring of the compute, storage and network resources of the AtlantECO GeoNode is provided through Amazon Cloud Watch²⁶ and includes:

- EC2 Server Status Checks
- EC2 CPU utilization (%)
- EBS Storage Volume Reads & Writes (Bytes)
- S3 Storage Volume (Bytes)
- Network In & Out
- Emails In & Out

From these, several KPI's could be calculated. AWS offers a Customer Carbon Footprint Tool²⁷ allows to calculate the Carbon Footprint of the AtlantECO GeoNode application, following Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Protocol²⁸ and ISO²⁹ standards. However, it can only report on carbon footprints larger than 0.1 MTCO_{2e} (Mega Tonnes CO₂ equivalent), a limit which is not reached due to the limited overall resources consumed by the GeoNode Infrastructure (currently it reports a carbon footprint of 0.0 MTCO_{2e})

6 Content workflow

We are adopting two different workflows to populate the content in the AtlantECO GeoNode, which differ in the type of data produced by the project. These are:

- AtlantECO BASE: Provided by WP2, Task 2.2, these are compilation of georeferenced observations, delivered in the form of relatively large (<= 26 GB) tabular data files (CSV or Microsoft Excel Files).
- AtlantECO GRID: Provided by WP2, Task 2.2, these are the gridded map products derived directly from the georeferenced observations as provided in AtlantECO BASE, delivered in the form of smaller multidimensional NetCDF files.
- AtlantECO MAPS: Provided by WP2, Task 2.3, these are extrapolated map products derived from the NetCDF files as provided in AtlantECO GRID, delivered in the form of a large number of small (<= 2 GB) multidimensional NetCDF files.

6.1 AtlantECO BASE

While it was not originally foreseen in the AtlantECO workplan to host these data files in the AtlantECO GeoNode, upon request of the project office, they will be published as remotely hosted documents. This avoids the additional storage and personnel costs involved in mapping these files into the spatial database. As a result, it will not be possible to visualise the ATLANTECO BASE datasets, though they will be searchable and downloadable from the GeoNode. As agreed, the workflow for AtlantECO BASE datasets contains following steps:

1. **Data Delivery:** Once finalized, WP2 will make the AtlantECO BASE datasets available in <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/BASE>, together with an initial set of placeholder metadata (e.g. title, keywords) for the GeoNode.
2. **Initial GeoNode population:** SBE will make the AtlantECO BASE datasets available through the ATLANTECO GeoNode, by linking to the datasets in <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/BASE>, and adding the placeholder metadata (Title,

²⁶ <https://aws.amazon.com/cloudwatch>

²⁷ <https://aws.amazon.com/aws-cost-management/aws-customer-carbon-footprint-tool/>

²⁸ <https://ghgprotocol.org/>

²⁹ <https://www3.epa.gov/ttnchie1/conference/ei16/session13/wintergreen.pdf>

Keywords). Initially the datasets in the GeoNode will be restricted to the GeoNode accounts of the WP2 partners to allow them to review and provide feedback on how the datasets look in the GeoNode. Once approved, the permissions can be updated as desired (available publicly or to specific GeoNode User Group, e.g. AtlantECO consortium).

3. **Metadata Delivery:** As documented in the Data Management Plan (D10.1), WP2 will submit the AtlantECO BASE to SEANOE³⁰, where they will provide a more complete set of minimal (ISO19115) metadata as curated by the SEANOE submission platform. Through this process, the data will be prepared for ingestion in EMODnet³¹, and the resulting metadata will be used to document the layers in the AtlantECO GeoNode.
4. **Final GeoNode population:** Once the AtlantECO BASE datasets are available and documented with metadata in SEANOE, SBE will update the AtlantECO BASE documents in the GeoNode with the metadata and data links from SEANOE.

6.2 AtlantECO MAPS

The content workflow for AtlantECO MAPS is described below. While the AtlantECO workplan indicates that the partners could upload the datasets themselves in the AtlantECO GeoNode, the sheer number of data files (> 1700) and variables (> 5 per data file) did not allow a manual content management approach. Instead, a semi-automated approach to populate the AtlantECO MAPS layers, their style (for interactive map visualisation) and metadata is being developed by SBE. It was originally foreseen (as per the Data Management Plan D10.1) that the AtlantECO MAPS data files would be accompanied by ISO19115 metadata (curated as part of the SEANOE submission) which is necessary for the GeoNode content population (distinguish the difference between the large amounts of map layers and make them searchable). As the submission and metadata collection processes have faced some delays, we are instead adopting the following two-stage content population approach:

1. **Data Delivery:** Once finalized, WP2 will make the AtlantECO MAPS datasets publicly available in <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS>, together with an initial set of placeholder metadata (e.g. title, keywords, style to be applied) for the GeoNode.
2. **Initial GeoNode population:** SBE will make the AtlantECO MAPS data available as interactive GeoNode layers, adding in the placeholder metadata (Title, Keywords). This will be performed using a semi-automated (scripted) approach. Initially the layers in the GeoNode will be restricted to the GeoNode accounts of the WP2 partners to allow them to review and provide feedback on how the datasets look (the applied style). Once approved, the permissions can be updated as desired (available publicly or to specific GeoNode User Group, e.g. AtlantECO consortium).
3. **Metadata Delivery:** As documented in the Data Management Plan (D10.1), WP2 will submit the AtlantECO MAPS to SEANOE, where they will provide a more complete set of minimal (ISO19115) metadata as curated by the SEANOE submission platform. Through this process, the data will be prepared for ingestion in EMODnet.
4. **Final GeoNode population:** Once the AtlantECO MAPS datasets have been documented with metadata in SEANOE, SBE will update the AtlantECO MAPS layers in the GeoNode with the metadata using the SEANOE OAI-PMH service³² and add links to the SEANOE submissions.

³⁰ <https://www.seanoe.org>

³¹ <https://www.seanoe.org/html/about.htm>

³² <https://www.seanoe.org/oai/>

7 Dissemination

7.1 Through the AtlantECO GeoNode Platform

Once populated, the AtlantECO GeoNode³³ will offer a platform for projects partners and wider stakeholders to search visualise and download the AtlantECO MAPS produced by the projects. AtlantECO BASE will be searchable and downloadable. Through its social features, partners and stakeholders will be able to rate and discuss data layers and share them to others either as links to specific data layers or embedding an Interactive GeoNode map in other websites (e.g. project or partner websites).

7.2 Through the European Atlas of the Seas

Administered by European Commission, Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE), the European Atlas of the Seas³⁴ is a freely available, web-based, interactive geographic information system delivering collections of maps derived from data on natural and socio-economic features in the marine and coastal regions of Europe and beyond. It aims to support non-specialist professionals in various sectors, such as non-governmental and policy-oriented professionals, and those involved in planning or executing projects related to the Blue Economy. Additionally, the Atlas intends to be a valuable educational tool for teachers and students, offering high-quality educational resources to enhance ocean literacy.

The hosting of AtlantECO MAPS In the GeoNode, makes these datasets available for visualisation through an Industry Standard OGC Web Mapping Service, which is Interoperable with the European Atlas of the Seas web map. As such, relevant map layers hosted In the AtlantECO GeoNode can be made available through the European Atlas of the Seas, which is managed by the EMODnet Secretariat, administered by SBE. This will disseminate the AtlantECO maps to the diverse and growing Atlas audience (over 110k visits in 2022) and unlock this information to ocean educators through the Ocean Literacy networks (e.g. Nausicaa, Escola Azul and EU4Ocean) engaged by the European Atlas of the Seas.

7.3 Through EMODnet

The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) is a network of European organizations working together to improve the FAIR'ness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) of marine data in Europe and increasingly globally. The goal of EMODnet is to provide a centralized portal where researchers, policymakers, and the public can easily access marine data from a wide range of sources. In addition, it leverages its vast collection of marine data to create marine data products that combines and harmonizes information on many ocean parameters at a European Scale. The EMODnet portal is coordinated by the EMODnet Secretariat, administered by SBE.

Through the submission of AtlantECO MAPS and BASE datasets in SEANOE (as described in section 5 of this Document), they will enter in the EMODnet Data Ingestion³⁵ pipeline, archiving them in the EU Marine Data Infrastructure and making them available to the users of EMODnet. This pipeline has two phases:

- Phase I: The submitted datasets and the curated metadata collected during the data submission process is published in the EMODnet Ingestion Submission Catalogue³⁶ In Its original format to make It available to EMODnet users as soon as possible

³³ <https://atlanteco-geonode.eu>

³⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/atlas/maritime_atlas

³⁵ <https://www.emodnet-ingestion.eu/>

³⁶ <https://www.emodnet-ingestion.eu/submissions/>

- Phase II: When possible, the datasets are further elaborated and integrated in national, European and EMODnet thematic databases and products.

8 Legacy period

As AtlantECO GeoNode is a project dissemination and exploitation tool, there is great value in keeping it operational for a legacy period after the end of the project. However, the operating costs of the cloud hosting environment during an extended legacy period are not foreseen in Seascope Belgium's resource allocation. With its current resources, Seascope Belgium can offer to keep the platform available for a one year period after the project end, though the costs of a more extended legacy period need to be negotiated with the Project Office.

During the legacy period, Seascope Belgium will maintain the AtlantECO GeoNode and its functionalities (e.g. security updates, incident management) but will no longer invest staff time to actively expand the data layer catalogue (it will remain as it was at the end of the project).

Practically, to cover the costs of the cloud hosting environment (AWS) during this legacy period, an estimated amount (average monthly bill * number of months of legacy period) will be billed and added to Seascope Belgium's AWS Advance Pay balance at the end of the project. This balance will subsequently be used to cover the monthly AWS bills for the AtlantECO GeoNode services after the project end.

9 References

Corti, P., Bartoli, F., Fabiani, A., Giovando, C., Kralidis, A.T. and Tzotsos, A. (2019) GeoNode: an open source framework to build spatial data infrastructures. PeerJ Preprints.

Annex I: AtlantECO GeoNode Practical Guide

This annex provides a practical guide to the AtlantECO GeoNode's terminology and basic functionalities like searching, visualising and downloading data layers. In addition, it explains how to create an interactive map from the data layers that can be used for further dissemination. Finally, it briefly shows how the data layers in the AtlantECO GeoNode can be accessed from the open-source desktop GIS software [QGIS](#).

GeoNode terminology

Layers

Layers are a primary component of the GeoNode. They are publishable resources representing a spatial data source (e.g. AtlantECO MAPS) which are associated with metadata, ratings, and comments.

Documents

Documents are any other files (e.g. AtlantECO Base data tables). which are associated with metadata, ratings and comments. They can be linked to specific data layers or maps.

Remote Services

In GeoNode, externally hosted data layers (e.g. on EMODnet) can be added through remote services. GeoNode supports the following web service protocols:

- OGC [Web Map Service](#)
- OGC [Web Map Tile Service](#)
- ArcGIS [REST Map Service](#)

Maps

Maps are combinations of various layers. They are fully interactive and can combine both layers in AtlantECO GeoNode as well as layers from remote services. Maps also contain other information such as map zoom and extent, layer ordering, filters, style and associated widgets.

How to search for data

From the AtlantECO GeoNode homepage you can use the free text search box to find layers, documents and maps that contain any matching text in the associated metadata.

Alternatively, you can browse the datasets by publication using the AtlantECO MAPS dropdown menu in the top bar.

Search for Data.

[Advanced Search](#)

 1 Map Data is available for browsing, aggregating and styling to generate maps which can be saved, downloaded, shared publicly or restricted to specify users only. Explore maps »	
 13 Users Geonode allows registered users to easily upload geospatial data and various documents in several formats. See users »	

[Privacy & Cookies Policy](#)

To browse through all layers, maps or documents, you can click the respective buttons on the home screen or alternatively access the Data > Layers tab, the Data > Documents tab or the Maps > Explore

Maps tab from the top bar respectively. This will open a search page which lists all layers, maps or documents that match your query. You can order the list of data by date, name or popularity. You can further refine your search using the different dropdown menus on the right, which allow to filter by:

- Text: free-text search field. This is recommended if you are looking for data on a specific species as it will auto-recommend content matching that query.
- Keywords: one or more hierarchical keywords. This allows you to browse through species, species groups, parameters, etc. for which data is available. Due to the considerable number of species for which data is available, it takes a few moments to load.
- Type: the data type (raster, vector, remote, document or map).
- Categories: the standardised ISO Geospatial Topic Category.
- Responsible: the person responsible or the point of contact for the data.
- Groups: the GeoNode groups to which data provider, creator or distributor belongs (e.g. their institute).
- Group Categories: The category to which this group belongs.
- Date: The publication date of the layer, document or map.
- Regions: The standard region associated which the layer, map or linked document.
- Extent: The geographic extent of the layer, map or document that overlaps with the extent of the interactive mini map. Pan and zoom in the mini map to refine your search.

Data ▾ Maps Apps About ▾

AtlantECO MAPS ▾

Search

Register

Sign in

Search :

Filters

Clear

929 found

01 ▾

TEXT

Search

KEYWORDS

TYPE

CATEGORIES

RESPONSIBLE

GROUPS

GROUP CATEGORIES

DATE

REGIONS

EXTENT

Global map of mean habitat suitability index for picozoa operative taxonomic unit (pOTU) 059 in the epipelagic depth zone (0-200 m) for the 2008-2017 period.

The NetCDF files contain the extrapolated maps of mean multi-year habitat suitability index (HSI) for each of 53 picozoa operative taxonomic units (pOTUs), as described in the manuscript Huber et al. 2024 (manuscript accepted

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Daniele De Angelis 20 Aug 2024 11 0 0

Global map of mean habitat suitability index for picozoa operative taxonomic unit (pOTU) 054 in the epipelagic depth zone (0-200 m) for the 2008-2017 period.

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Daniele De Angelis 20 Aug 2024 3 0 0

How to visualise data and metadata

Clicking on the data layer of interest will open up the layer overview page with an interactive map of the data layer, its basic metadata and buttons to download the data layer, view detailed metadata, visualise the data in full screen mode, or download the metadata.

AtlantECO MAPS | Search | Register | Sign in

Monthly mean of species richness of Amphipods for the 2012-2031 period

Download Layer | **Metadata Detail** | View Layer | Download Metadata

Legend
Mean species richness Amphipoda 2012-2031

Maps using this layer
List of maps using this layer:
Example Map

Styles
The following styles are associated with this layer. Choose a style to view it in the preview map.
 (default style) Mean species richness Amphipoda 2012-2031

About
Responsible, Point of Contact, Metadata Author
 FabioBenedetti
ETH Zürich

Info | Attributes | Share | Ratings | Comments

Title Monthly mean of species richness of Amphipods for the 2012-2031 period
License Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)
Abstract Ensemble projections of monthly surface species richness (i.e., computed through the sum of species-level habitat suitabilities) based on three standard species distribution models (GLM, GAM and ANN) trained on global presence data with a group-level target background for pseudoabsence data (full methodology described in Benedetti et al., 2021)
Publication Date July 31, 2023, 10:07 a.m.
Type Raster Data
Keywords

- AtlantECO MAPS
- surface species richness
- 2012-2031
- Benedetti et al. 2021
- Amphipoda
- mean

Category Oceans
Regions Global
Responsible FabioBenedetti
Group Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich (ETHZ)
DOI <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25385-x>
More info -

The interactive map allows you to visualise the data layer. You are able to pan (drag & drop), zoom (scroll or +/- button) and interact with the data by clicking a specific location on the map. This will return the value of the raster at this location. In case the layer has a time dimension, you are able to step through the time steps with the back and forward buttons or play the timesteps as an animation with the play/pause button. The background map can be altered by clicking the background layer thumbnail in the lower right and selecting the background layer of choice. On the right, you can view the legend for the data, links to maps that are using this layer, the available styles for the layer, and the data responsible, point of contact and metadata author.

Below the map, under the Info tab, you are able to view basic metadata of the layer like title, license, abstract, publication date, keywords, category, region and owner. To view the full set of metadata, click on the “Metadata Detail” button in the top right. Under the attributes tab, you find additional metadata on the attribute fields (in case of vector type data).

This requires you to be logged in with an AtlantECO GeoNode Account. To create one go [here](#).

This page also offers social features through the Share, Ratings and Comments tabs. Under the Favorites tab, you can add the map to your GeoNode profile for easy access.

How to download data and metadata

Download data layer

Data layers can be downloaded through the “Download Layer” button in the top right. This will open the download layer menu.

Under the Images tab, you have the option to download a georeferenced image of the data in following formats:

- JPEG
- PDF
- PNG

Under the Data tab, you can download the actual dataset in a format of choice. For raster data types following formats are available:

- GeoTIFF

Download metadata

The metadata of a layer can be downloaded through the “Download Metadata” button in the top right. This will open the metadata download menu.

From this menu, the full metadata can be downloaded for viewing in simple text or html format. Furthermore, following standard metadata xml formats for machine parsing are supported:

- ISO

- FGDC
- ebRIM
- Dublin Core
- DIF
- Atom

How to create and share an interactive map

This requires you to be logged in with an AtlantECO GeoNode Account. To create one go [here](#).

To create a new map, click the Maps > Create Map tab. Alternatively, from the layer search page, click the “+” icon next to the layers you wish to combine in a map. The selected maps are listed in the top left. To combine them in a map, click “Create a Map”.

The screenshot shows the 'Explore Layers' page on the AtlantECO GeoNode. The top navigation bar includes 'Data', 'Maps', 'Apps', and 'About'. The 'Maps' dropdown menu is open, showing 'Explore Maps' and 'Create Map'. The user is logged in as 'Tim Collart'. The main content area is titled 'Explore Layers' and shows '927 Layers found'. On the left, there is a 'Selection' panel with two search filters and a 'Filters' section with various categories like 'TEXT', 'KEYWORDS', 'TYPE', 'CATEGORIES', 'RESPONSIBLE', 'GROUPS', 'GROUP CATEGORIES', 'DATE', 'REGIONS', and 'EXTENT'. The 'Raster Layer' filter is selected, showing '927' results. The main list displays two search results for 'Global map of mean habitat suitability index for picozoa operative taxonomic unit (pOTU) 059 in the epipelagic depth zone (0-200 m) for the 2008-2017 period' and 'Global map of mean habitat suitability index for picozoa operative taxonomic unit (pOTU) 054 in the epipelagic depth zone (0-200 m) for the 2008-2017 period'. Each result includes a thumbnail map, a title, a description, and a 'Create a Map' button.

This will take you to the Map Composer, either an empty map with only base layer or the selected layers on top of the base layer. The basemap can be changed by clicking the background layer thumbnail in the lower right and selecting the background layer of choice. Open the layer menu by clicking the layers icon in the top left.

Add layers

To add data layers from the GeoNode click on the add layer button on the top left. This will open a catalogue window on the right-hand side. To add layers to your map select them and hit the Add Layers '+' button. When finished you may hit Done to close the dialog and go back to the map.

Reordering and removing Layers

Change the display order of the layers listed in the data tab by simply dragging and dropping their names. The order in the map will be updated to reflect that. You can show/hide the layer legend with the arrow on the right-hand side of the layer box. To turn a layer's visibility off simply press the eye symbol. You can also gradually change the layer opacity with the slider at the bottom of the layer box.

When you click a layer in the layer menu, it becomes highlighted in blue, and several buttons appear on the top of the menu. From left to right:

- Zoom the map to the extent of the layer.
- Change the settings for the layer (style to use, tooltip to display, etc.).
- Delete the layer.
- Download the data layer in the desired format.
- Compare two overlying layers (tool demonstrated in the screenshot below).

Saving your map

Once a suitable set of layers and zoom level has been found it's time to save it so others can see it. From the top right menu icon, choose save as.

This opens a menu that allows you to add a thumbnail, title and description to your map.

Sharing a Map

Any map from the AtlantECO GeoNode can be shared through a link or embedded for use on another site or blog. To share a map, choose share from the top right menu icon. This generates the share link, or the iframe snippet to include in the html of another website.

Access the AtlantECO GeoNode in QGIS

QGIS is an open-source GIS tool that allows visualising and analysing geospatial data. It can be connected to the AtlantECO GeoNode to directly pull data into your own GIS project.

From the QGIS browser panel, right click GeoNode > New Connection.

In the resulting dialogue box, fill in a name for the GeoNode connection and the AtlantECO GeoNode URL: <https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/> and click 'OK'.

Create a New GeoNode Connection

Connection Details

Name AtlantECO GeoNode

URL https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/

WFS Options

Version Maximum Detect

Max. number of features

Enable feature paging

Page size

Ignore axis orientation (WFS 1.1/WFS 2.0)

Invert axis orientation

Use GML2 encoding for transactions

WMS/WMTS Options

DPI-Mode all

Ignore GetMap/GetTile/GetLegendGraphic URI reported in capabilities

Ignore GetFeatureInfo URI reported in capabilities

Ignore axis orientation (WMS 1.3/WMTS)

Ignore reported layer extents

Invert axis orientation

Smooth pixmap transform

Test Connection

OK Cancel Help

From the QGIS browser panel, you can now load all the content from the AtlantECO GeoNode (note that due to the considerable number of layers, QGIS takes a while to render the content depending on your internet connection). It presents two menus:

- **WCS:** This web coverage service allows you to load the data from the layers into QGIS. Use this if you want to visualise the data with your own color scale or perform analyses on the data.
- **WMS:** This web mapping service allows you to add georeferenced images from the data to QGIS, using the color scale defined on the GeoNode. Use this for quick visualisation of a layer.

